

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

November, 05-06 2022
Ethno Complex Vrđnickska kula, Vrđnik

MODERN TECHNIQUES OF IRRADIATION OF THE LEFT BREAST-ABC SYSTEM

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Introduction: In order to prevent early and late complications after irradiation of the left breast region, new techniques and means of immobilization have been introduced that allow the patient to have no or minimal unwanted side effects during and after therapy.

Goal: Prevention or mitigation of early and late complications during and after radiation

Methodology: Application of modern irradiation methods with adequate immobilization

Result: The quality and length of life of patients after completed radiotherapy is at a high level.

Conclusion: The task of radiotherapy is to precisely irradiate a malignant tumor with maximum sparing of healthy surrounding tissue and organs. For this purpose, the application of new techniques, i.e. irradiation. the introduction of the ABC system provides opportunities to maximally save organs from risks such as the heart, and therefore morbidity and mortality from heart disease is reduced to a minimum or completely absent after irradiation of the left breast.

Keywords: technique, radiotherapy, left breast

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2022**

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Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

CIP – Каталогizacija u publikaciji
Biblioteka Mатице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (2022 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress,
November, 05-06 2022 Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula,
Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. - Novi Sad : Institut za
Onkologiju Vojvodine, 2022 (Novi Sad : NS digiprint).
– 56 str. : ilustr. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200.

ISBN 978-86-82113-15-7

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 78911241